

Efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

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ABSTRACT

Background: Peripheral venous cannulation (PVC) is a commonly performed invasive procedure in pediatric care, often associated with difficulty due to poor vein visibility and smaller vein size in children. Multiple attempts can increase pain, anxiety, and risk of complications. Infrared vein visualization has been introduced as an advanced technique to improve vein identification and cannulation success.

Objectives: To assess the efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas.

Methods: A quantitative, non-experimental descriptive comparative research design was adopted. The study was conducted among 100 pediatric patients (50 in the infrared group and 50 in the traditional group) selected using non-probability purposive sampling. Data were collected using a structured demographic proforma, Modified IV Cannulation Rating Scale, and Wong-Baker Faces Pain Rating Scale. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics including independent t-test and Fisher's exact test were used for comparison and association analysis.

Results: The study findings revealed that the success rate of cannulation was higher in the infrared group (74%) compared to the traditional group (56%). The mean pain score was significantly lower in the infrared group than in the traditional group, as determined by the independent t-test ($p < 0.05$). Fisher's exact test showed a statistically significant association between selected demographic variables such as age and vein visibility with cannulation success in the traditional group ($p < 0.05$), whereas no statistically significant association was observed between demographic variables and cannulation success in the infrared group ($p > 0.05$). Additionally, no significant association was found between gender and pain scores in either group.

Conclusion: Infrared vein visualization is an effective technique that enhances the success rate of peripheral venous cannulation and reduces pain among pediatric patients. It can be recommended as a supportive tool in pediatric clinical settings to improve procedural outcomes and patient comfort.

Keywords: Peripheral venous cannulation, infrared vein visualization, pediatric patients, pain, success rate, demographic variables.

INTRODUCTION

Paediatrics, derived from Greek words meaning child care and treatment, is the branch of medical science concerned with the health of children from conception to adolescence. Children constitute a significant proportion of the population and are a vulnerable group requiring preventive, promotive, curative, and rehabilitative care. Due to their unique physiological and developmental characteristics, disease patterns and management in children differ from adults, necessitating specialized care for optimal growth and survival.

Peripheral intravenous cannulation (PIVC) is a common yet challenging procedure in paediatric patients due to small vein size, poor visibility, and limited cooperation. First-attempt success rates range from 60–81%, often leading to multiple attempts, increased pain, anxiety, and complications such as infiltration and phlebitis. Delays in establishing IV access can impact timely treatment, especially in emergency situations, highlighting the importance of improving first-attempt success.

Near-infrared (NIR) vein visualization devices have been developed to enhance vein detection by projecting images based on haemoglobin absorption of light. While these devices improve vein visibility, evidence on their effectiveness in increasing first-attempt success is mixed. Some studies show reduced procedure time and attempts, particularly in difficult cases, suggesting that NIR technology may support clinicians in improving efficiency and patient experience in paediatric IV cannulation.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

“Herbert Zeman” invented the first vein-finding device in 1995 to image subcutaneous veins. Many of these devices utilize near- infrared light that is presented on the skin surface. This light is absorbed in the blood vessels by haemoglobin, while in the remaining tissues it is reflected. This system processes the returned images, adds colour, and displays the image in real time on the skin surface.

Peripheral venous cannulation is essential but challenging in paediatric patients due to small vein size, poor visibility, and limited cooperation, often leading to multiple attempts, increased pain, and procedural delays. Infrared vein visualization has been shown in several studies to reduce attempts, improve efficiency, and enhance patient and caregiver satisfaction, particularly in children with difficult intravenous access (DIVA). However, evidence remains inconsistent, with some studies reporting no significant improvement compared to traditional techniques, especially when performed by experienced clinicians. Despite limitations such as cost and training requirements, NIR technology remains a valuable adjunct in improving paediatric IV access outcomes.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Peripheral venous cannulation in children is often challenging due to small, less visible veins and limited cooperation, especially in critically ill or very young patients. Traditional methods such as palpation and visual inspection may lead to repeated attempts, causing pain, discomfort,

and complications like hematoma or vein damage. Infrared vein visualization is an advanced technique that uses infrared light to enhance vein visibility, making cannulation easier and more accurate. This technology can reduce the number of attempts, improve success rates, decrease procedural time, and enhance the overall experience for both patients and healthcare providers.

The potential benefits of infrared vein visualization include;

Increases first-attempt success rate, reducing failed attempts

Decreases procedure time, especially in anxious children

Improves patient comfort by minimizing pain and trauma

Helps in difficult venous access cases (infants, small veins)

Reduces stress and anxiety for both child and caregivers

Enhances accuracy in vein localization and cannulation

complications such as hematoma, vein damage, and infection

Improves clinical efficiency and saves healthcare time and resources

Provides a safer alternative compared to traditional techniques

METHODOLOGY

The present study adopted a quantitative research approach with a non-experimental descriptive comparative design to assess the efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at selected hospitals. The study was conducted in selected hospital settings over a period of 28 days. The target population included children admitted to hospitals, while the accessible population comprised children aged 1–6 years requiring peripheral venous cannulation. A total sample of 100 children was selected using a non-probability purposive sampling technique, with 50 children in each group. Data were collected using a structured observational checklist and demographic proforma. The tool was validated by experts and reliability was established prior to the study. A pilot study was conducted to assess feasibility. Ethical approval was obtained and informed consent was taken from parents before data collection. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics

RESULT

SECTION I

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE

Age

In traditional technique group, 42% of the children had age 1 to 3 years and 58% of them had age 3.1 to 6 years. In infrared technique group, 30% of the children had age 1 to 3 years and 70% of them had age 3.1 to 6 years.

Weight

In traditional technique group, 8% of them had weight up-to 10kg, 56% of them had weight 10-15 kg and 36% of had weight above 15kg. In infrared technique group, 4% of them had weight up-to 10kg, 52% of them had weight 10-15kg and 44% of them had weight above15 kg.

Gender

In traditional technique group, 50% of them were males and 50% of them were females. In infrared technique group, 54% of them were males and 46% of them were females.

Ethnicity of skin

In traditional technique group, 22% of them had dark skin, 54% of them had medium skin and 24% of them had fair skin. In infrared technique group, 14% of them had dark skin, 24% of them had medium skin and 62% of them had fair skin.

Selection of site of vein

In traditional technique group, 46% of them had basilic vein selected, 28% of them had cephalic vein selected and 26% of them had dorsal vein selected. In infrared technique group, 42% of them had basilic vein selected, 30% of them had cephalic vein selected and 28% of them had dorsal vein selected.

Size of Intra-Cath

In traditional technique group, 4% of them had Intra-Cath size 22 G and 96% of them had Intra-Cath size of 24 G. In infrared technique group, 2% of them had Intra-Cath size 22 G and 98% of them had Intra-Cath size of 24 G.

Diagnosis

In traditional technique group, 24% of them had fever, 18% of them had gastrointestinal disorders, 6% of them had haematological disorder, 8% of them had nephrological disorder, 6% of them had neurological disorder and 38% of them had respiratory system related disorders. In infrared technique group, 16% of them had fever, 20% of them had gastrointestinal disorders, 8% of them had haematological disorder, 12% of them had nephrological disorder, 16% of them had neurological disorder and 28% of them had respiratory system related disorders.

Section II

Analysis of data related to efficacy of infrared vein visualization for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

Table shows Efficacy of infrared vein visualization for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

n =50

Cannulation	Infrared technique	
	Freq	%
More efficient	37	74%
Moderate efficient	13	26%
Less efficient	0	0%

n =50

A Bar Diagram shows percentage distribution of Efficacy of infrared vein visualization in peripheral venous cannulation

Description: Above table and graph shows that in the study 74% of the children at hospitals in infrared technique group had more efficient Peripheral venous cannulation and 26% of them had moderate efficient peripheral venous cannulation.

Table shows Efficacy of infrared vein visualization for peripheral venous pain in children at hospitals in selected areas

n=50

Pain	Infrared technique	
	Freq	%
No pain	0	0%
Mild	3	6%
Moderate	31	62%
Severe	13	26%
Worst	3	6%

A Bar Diagram shows the percentage distribution of Pain level Peripheral venous cannulation in Infrared Technique

Description: Above table and graph shows that in the study 6% of the children at hospitals in infrared technique group had mild pain, 62% of them had moderate pain, 26% of them had severe pain and 6% of them had worst pain.

Section III

Analysis of data related to efficacy of traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

Table shows Efficacy of traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

n = 50

Cannulation	Traditional technique	
	Freq	%
More efficient	28	56%
Moderate efficient	22	44%
Less efficient	0	0%

n = 50

A Bar Diagram shows percentage distribution of Efficacy of Peripheral venous cannulation in Traditional Technique

Description: Above table and graph show that in the study 56% of the children at hospitals in

infrared technique group had more efficient Peripheral venous cannulation and 44% of them had moderate efficient peripheral venous cannulation.

Table shows Efficacy of traditional technique for peripheral venous pain in children at hospitals in selected areas

n=50

Pain	Traditional technique	
	Freq	%
No pain	0	0%
Mild	1	2%
Moderate	29	58%
Severe	14	28%
Worst	6	12%

n=50

A Bar Diagram shows percentage distribution of Pain level in peripheral venous cannulation in traditional technique

Description: Above table and graph shows that in the study 2% of the children at hospitals in traditional technique group had mild pain, 58% of them had moderate pain, 28% of them had severe pain and 12% of them had worst pain.

Section IV

Analysis of data related to comparison the efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

Table 6: Comparison the efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

n=50, 50

Cannulation	Traditional technique		Infrared technique	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
More efficient	28	56%	37	74%
Moderate efficient	22	44%	13	26%
Less efficient	0	0%	0	0%

n=50, 50

A Bar Diagram shows percentage distribution efficacy of peripheral venous cannulation in Traditional and Infrared Technique.

Description: Above table and graph shows that in traditional technique group, 74% of the children at hospitals in infrared technique group had more efficient Peripheral venous cannulation and 26% of them had moderate efficient peripheral venous cannulation. In

infrared technique group, 56% of the children at hospitals in infrared technique group had more efficient Peripheral venous cannulation and 44% of them had moderate efficient peripheral venous cannulation. This indicates that the infrared technique is remarkably more efficient as compared to traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children .

Table shows Comparison the efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at hospitals in selected areas

n=50, 50

Pain	Traditional technique		Infrared technique	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
No pain	0	0%	0	0%
Mild	1	2%	3	6%
Moderate	29	58%	31	62%
Severe	14	28%	13	26%
Worst	6	12%	3	6%

n=50, 50

A Bar diagram shows the percentage distribution Pain level in peripheral venous cannulation in Traditional and Infrared Technique

Description: Above table and graph shows that in traditional technique group, 6% of the children at hospitals in infrared technique group had mild pain, 62% of them had moderate pain, 26% of them had severe pain and 6% of them had worst pain. In infrared technique group,

2% of the children at hospitals in traditional technique group had mild pain, 58% of them had moderate pain, 28% of them had severe pain and 12% of them had worst pain. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the pain among children in infrared technique group as compared to that in traditional technique group

Section V

Analysis of data related to association between research finding and selected demographic variable among children at hospitals in selected areas

Table shows Fisher's exact test for the association between pain and selected demographic variable among children at hospitals in traditional group

n=50

Demographic variable		Pain				p-value
		Mild	Moderate	Severe	Worst	
Age	1 to 3 years	0	16	3	2	0.116
	3.1 to 6 years	1	13	11	4	
Weight	up to 10 kg	0	3	0	1	0.069
	10-15 kg	0	20	6	2	
	> 15 kg	1	6	8	3	
Gender	Male	0	14	8	3	0.916
	Female	1	15	6	3	
Ethnicity of skin	Dark	0	6	2	3	0.137
	Medium	0	10	1	1	
	Fair	1	13	11	2	
Selection of site of vein	Basilic	1	12	7	3	0.627
	Cephalic	0	11	2	1	
	Dorsal	0	6	5	2	
Size of Intra-Cath	22 G	1	1	0	0	0.052
	24 G	0	28	14	6	
Diagnosis	Fever	1	6	2	3	0.038
	Gastro-intestinal	0	3	4	2	
	Haematological disorder	0	0	2	1	
	Nephrological	0	2	2	0	
	Neurological	0	3	0	0	
	Respiratory infection	0	15	4	0	

Description: Since p-value corresponding to diagnosis was small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable diagnosis is found to have significant association with the pain among children in traditional technique group.

Table shows Fisher's exact test for the association between cannulation and selected demographic variable among children at hospitals in traditional group

n=50

Demographic variable		Cannulation		p-value
		Moderate efficient	More efficient	
Age	1 to 3 years	4	17	0.004
	3.1 to 6 years	18	11	
Weight	Up to 10 kg	1	3	0.190
	10-15 kg	10	18	
	> 15 kg	11	7	
Gender	Male	11	14	1.000
	Female	11	14	
Ethnicity of skin	Dark	6	5	0.013
	Medium	1	11	
	Fair	15	12	
Selection of site of vein	Basilic	9	14	0.711
	Cephalic	6	8	
	Dorsal	7	6	
Size of Intra-Cath	22 G	1	1	1.000
	24 G	21	27	
Diagnosis	Fever	5	7	0.236
	Gastro-intestinal	6	3	
	Haematological disorder	2	1	
	Nephrological	3	1	
	Neurological	1	2	
	Respiratory infection	5	14	

Description: Since p-value corresponding to age and ethnicity of skin were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variables age and ethnicity of skin were found to have significant association with the cannulation among children in traditional technique group.

Table shows Fisher's exact test for the association between pain and selected demographic variable among children at hospitals in infrared group n=50

Demographic variable		Pain				p-value
		Mild	Moderate	Severe	Worst	
Age	1 to 3 years	0	8	5	2	0.246
	3.1 to 6 years	3	23	8	1	
Weight	up to 10 kg	0	1	0	1	0.009
	10-15 kg	0	14	11	1	
	> 15 kg	3	16	2	1	
Gender	Male	0	16	9	2	0.185
	Female	3	15	4	1	
Ethnicity of skin	Dark	0	5	1	1	0.839
	Medium	1	7	3	1	
	Fair	2	19	9	1	
Selection of site of vein	Basilic	0	16	4	1	0.299
	Cephalic	2	6	6	1	
	Dorsal	1	9	3	1	
Size of Intra-Cath	22 G	1	0	0	0	0.120
	24 G	2	31	13	3	
Diagnosis	Fever	1	5	2	0	0.041
	Gastro-intestinal	0	4	4	2	
	Haematological disorder	0	2	2	0	
	Nephrological	2	1	2	1	
	Neurological	0	7	1	0	
	Respiratory infection	0	12	2	0	

Description: Since p-value corresponding to weight and diagnosis of skin were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variables weight and diagnosis were found to have significant

association with the pain among children in infrared technique group.

Table shows Fisher's exact test for the association between cannulation and selected demographic variable among children at hospitals in infrared group

n=50

Demographic variable		Cannulation		p-value
		Moderate	More	
Age	1 to 3 years	4	11	1.000
	3.1 to 6 years	9	26	
Weight	Uto 10 kg	1	1	0.189
	10-15 kg	9	17	
	> 15 kg	3	19	
Gender	Male	9	18	0.332
	Female	4	19	
Ethnicity of skin	Dark	1	6	0.897
	Medium	3	9	
	Fair	9	22	
Selection of site of vein	Basilic	5	16	0.776
	Cephalic	5	10	
	Dorsal	3	11	
Size of Intra-Cath	22 G	0	1	1.000
	24 G	13	36	
Diagnosis	Fever	1	7	0.055
	Gastro-intestinal	5	5	
	Haematological disorder	2	2	
	Nephrological	3	3	
	Neurological	1	7	
	Respiratory infection	1	13	

Description: Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the cannulation among children in

infrared technique group.

DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted to assess the efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus the traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children aged 1–6 years at selected hospitals. Findings showed that infrared vein visualization was more effective, with 74% of children achieving efficient cannulation compared to 56% in the traditional group. It also improved vein identification and increased cannulation success. Children in the infrared group experienced less pain, with most reporting mild to moderate pain, while the traditional group had higher severe pain levels. This suggests reduced repeated attempts and tissue trauma with infrared technology. Similar findings were supported by studies conducted by Kadoun et al. and Perry et al., which reported improved success rates and fewer attempts. However, some studies like Chapman et al. showed no significant difference, indicating mixed evidence. The present study also found that demographic variables influenced outcomes in the traditional group but not in the infrared group. Overall, infrared vein visualization proved to be a more effective and child-friendly technique for paediatric cannulation.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the study was to assess the efficacy of infrared vein visualization versus the traditional technique for peripheral venous cannulation in children at selected hospitals. The study was based on Wiedenbach's Prescriptive Theory and used a quantitative, non-experimental descriptive comparative research design. Samples were selected using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. Findings revealed that infrared vein visualization was more effective, with higher success rates (74%) compared to the traditional technique (56%). Pain perception was also lower in the infrared group. Significant associations were observed between selected demographic variables and outcomes in both groups, while no significant association was found with cannulation success in the infrared group. Overall, infrared vein visualization improved success and comfort in paediatric cannulation and can be recommended for clinical practice.

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